

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D1.3: Treatment and processing activities for mineral and bio-organic waste

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from [01/09/2023] to [31/12/2024]
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Contents:

A) Main objectives achieved

Table - List of Deliverables (M1: January 2023)

NUM	DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEM IN ACTION LEVEL**	DUE DATE
D1.1	Collection of data, processing technologies	R	A database and a report on collected information (production, characteristics, and localisation data, together with representative processing technologies).	POLITO	PU	M9
D1.2	Characterization of waste and new products from Mineral and bio-organic waste.	DB	A database reporting the characteristics of the investigated mineral and organic waste and (recycled) products obtained after treatment activities (described in T1.3) will be delivered. Together with it, an operative manual to populate and fill the database will be also produced.	UNITO	PU	M22
D1.3	Treatment and processing activities for mineral and bio-organic waste	R	A report on the investigated treatment activities (methodologies, procedures, limits, etc.) will be produced.	UNITO	PU	M24
D1.4	Pilot Sites Recycled Products Application	R	Pilot sites to test and validate the proposed technologies will be assessed	UNITO	PU	M32

Table - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
MS1.1	Treatment Activities for EQW, CDW, EW	1	12	Planning and authorisation delivered
MS1.2	Data collection and processing of EQW, CDW, EW, CW	1	12	Collection of data and processing info for LCA within the due date (LCA linked to RM6)
MS1.3	Pilot Sites testing activities	1	18	Planning and authorisation delivered
MS1.4	Recycled Products Application (from MW/OBW)	1	24	Planning and authorisation delivered

A) Main objectives achieved

1. The application of the treatment and processing activities to treat mineral [extractive quarry (EW), construction and demolition waste (CDW), excavation waste (EW) and ceramic waste (CW)] and bio-organic waste.
2. The description of the investigated treatment activities according to the methodologies and procedures used as well as the limits that were encountered.
3. During the 16 months of the Task D1.3, the research teams established the treatments and processing activities used to treat the mineral and bio-organic wastes

The main results of the Task D1.3 are:

1. The implementation of the database from the Task D1.2 reporting the investigated treatment activities according to methodologies, procedures and encountered limitations. The implemented database can be found at the following link <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1rg8c7fUxPHxFq8HSx38ujt8Y7dEf9c7c/edit?gid=1636938657#gid=1636938657>
2. The development of a report with the collected information in the database

A) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

During the activities of Task D1.3, all the seven working groups defined in the Task (Task D1.1) have continued to work on the application of treatment and processing activities to produce the new products starting from mineral or bio-organic wastes.

The research teams defined the protocols related to the investigated treatment activities focusing on methodologies and procedures used and on the limitations encountered. Below, there are reported the list of each research team and the description of the treatment and processing activities performed.

Research Team A

Technosols production

The studied process involves the production of technosols (artificial new soils) using different materials and intentionally modelling them to provide suitable materials for urban greenery, to prevent erosion and floods or for to rehabilitate and regenerate urban, industrial or contaminated/degraded areas. In the same context, herein technosols will be defined as a man-made soil constituted of various materials (urban/industrial wastes, natural materials, deep horizons soils, etc...) that contribute in boosting circular economy, favoring ground stability/site rehabilitation and enhancing urban landscape.

In urban areas, construction and demolition wastes (herein denoted as CDW) represent the main source of wastes and are thus, together with excavated soils, good candidates for technosols design.

For the process, the waste inorganic materials were collected from a treatment plant which processes natural aggregates, CDW, rocks and soils. The organic materials were provided by a local composting plant. In laboratory, 10 technosols combinations were tested, with two criteria: i) providing a low-cost, minimal composition (three components), which guarantees the economic applicability and transferability from mesocosm to a large scale; ii) limiting the use of natural soil to preserve a non-renewable resource, thus using the maximum quantity of wastes, testing the dose-response effect with regard to plant growth and phytotoxicity.

In the field pilot sites, the best 4 combinations were tested, together with a control natural soil. In all combinations we used:

- CDW: recovered aggregates produced from the plant (0-5.6 mm) after some simple phases of collection of CDW, removal of unwanted materials (e.g., wood, plastic) and crushing and sieving phases.
- Compost produced from the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) and green mulched residues.
- Excavated natural soil, sieved at 5.6mm to exclude larger particles that could change the comparability with the recovered CDW.

Once sampled, the materials were characterized with chemical and physical analyses to ensure the absence of contaminants and to define the suitability to be used as technosols with regard to fertility and size of particles. In particular, the parameters determined with the official Italian methods were: pH, electrical conductivity, texture, density, total carbon and nitrogen, carbonates, bioavailable P, cation exchange capacity (CEC), nitrates, inorganic contaminants

(total content), leachable cations and anions (UNI EN 12457 - 2004). Physical analyses were carried out to determine size distribution (EN933-1, 2012, adapted using wet separation) and plasticity (Atterberg limits' tests, ASTM D4318 – 00, ASTM D427 – 04, ASTM D4943 – 02) of the investigated samples.

Technosols fertility was assessed through seed germination tests (assessed through incubators, for 48h at 27°C) and plant growth tests (15 days) using model species (*Lepidium Sativum L.* - Garden Cress).

The mixes chosen for the pilot tests contained different percentages of CDW (50-80%), compost (10-30%) and excavated soil (0-20%) and were compared with the excavated soil alone. Each mix was prepared in 4 replicates in mesocosms (600 L) placed in three experimental areas within the city of Alpignano (TO). All the mesocosms have been filled with one layer of recycled CDW for drainage (20 cm at the bottom, 50-70 mm fraction) and one layer of technosols mix (40 cm).

To test the ability of the mixes to sustain plant growth and development in real conditions, 2 plant species used in urban landscaping were chosen: *Stachys lanata* and *Saponaria officinalis*.

In all the boxes the 2 plant species were planted, 3 plants for each species, 6 in total for each box.

For the next 3 years, biometric data on plant development, health status and physiological status will be collected on a monthly basis. The evaluated species will also be studied for their soil coverage capacity to counteract the development of weeds. The soils will be sampled every six months to evaluate the evolution of the fertility of the substrate mixtures and the pedogenesis.

Operational Process for Circular Plasters Experimentation

The experimentation process for circular plasters involves a structured approach, ensuring thorough material evaluation and optimized performance.

Below is a step-by-step description of the process:

Input Material Characterization

The initial phase focuses on analysing the properties of the input materials—lime putty, quarry waste powder, rice husk, hemp, and cork shavings. Each material undergoes rigorous chemical, physical, and microstructural evaluations, such as XRD, XRF, SEM, FT-IR, and granulometric analyses. These tests ensure the suitability of materials for sustainable and effective plaster formulations.

Mixing and Formulation

Based on the input material properties, various mixtures are prepared by adjusting the proportions of lime, quarry waste powder, and organic components. The aim is to identify optimal combinations that balance workability, strength, and environmental sustainability.

Preliminary Observations

Fresh plaster samples are assessed for key physical properties, including:

Consistency: Measured using UNI EN 1015-3 standards.

Setting Time: Evaluated per UNI EN 196-3.

Air Content: Determined as per UNI EN 1015-7.

These tests ensure the feasibility of application and the performance of fresh mixtures.

Laboratory Testing

Cured plaster samples undergo comprehensive testing to evaluate mechanical, physical, thermal, and durability properties:

Mechanical Strength: Compressive and flexural strength (UNI EN 1015-11).

Adhesion to Substrate: Pull-off test (UNI EN 1015-12).

Surface Analysis: Contact angle and density measurements

Thermal analysis: TGA, and DSC analyses.

Whether these tests should also be carried out is under consideration:

Water Absorption and Vapor Permeability: UNI EN 1015-18 and UNI EN 1015-19.

Durability: Freeze-thaw resistance (UNI EN 1015-21) and salt crystallization (UNI EN 12370).

Thermal Properties: Thermal conductivity (UNI EN 12667).

Validation of Mix

The best-performing formulations will be validated based on laboratory test results, focusing on strength, adhesion, sustainability, and compatibility with construction standards.

On-Site Pilot Testing

The selected mixes are applied at a pilot site to assess real-world performance. Key evaluations include:

Ease of application and workability.

Resistance to environmental factors such as UV exposure, temperature variations, and moisture.

Monitoring for crack formation and long-term durability.

This process exemplifies a holistic approach to developing sustainable construction materials, combining traditional craftsmanship with modern testing methodologies. It aligns with the principles of the circular economy, promoting innovative solutions for eco-friendly building practices.

Reinforced Embankments for Road Construction and Natural Hazard Protection

Project Objective

The primary aim of the project is to assess the performance and feasibility of sustainable materials in geotechnical applications.

This involves the use of recycled aggregates from construction and demolition (C&D) waste combined with excavated soils, reinforced with geogrids.

Project Phases and Methodology

A. Laboratory Characterization Tests

Preliminary evaluation of the properties of recycled aggregates, excavated soils, and their mixtures.

B. In situ Experimental Tests

Construction of reinforced embankments using mixtures of recycled aggregates and excavated soils.

Key Objectives:

- Evaluate structural integrity and stability under real-world conditions.
- Compare performance with conventional construction materials.
- Pull-Out Tests - Analysis of geogrid-material interactions with recycled mixtures.
- Performance comparison between recycled and natural aggregates.

Preliminary Findings

A. Performance of Recycled Materials

Recycled aggregates from C&D waste exhibit comparable performance to conventional materials.

These materials contribute to environmental sustainability and resource recovery.

B. Pull-Out Resistance

Comparable pull-out resistance values were observed for geogrid-recycled aggregate interactions and geogrid-natural aggregate interactions.

Results align with existing literature, highlighting the critical role of material-geosynthetic interactions in reinforced embankments.

Innovative Impact of the Project

A. Large-Scale Validation

This study provides the first empirical evidence supporting the use of recycled aggregates in reinforced embankments under real-world conditions.

It addresses a significant research gap, as prior studies have primarily focused on laboratory-scale experiments.

B. Implications for Geotechnical Engineering

Offers practical insights for the adoption of sustainable materials.

Contributes to the development of design guidelines for future infrastructure projects.

First Conclusions

Preliminary results demonstrate the potential of recycled materials for sustainable geotechnical applications.

These findings promote resource efficiency and innovation in engineering practices.

Research Team B

The ongoing work is based on a series of experiments aimed at analyzing possible alterations in the composition, mechanical and physical properties of carbonate and dolomitic rocks subjected to extreme climatic and environmental conditions. The aim of the work is also to verify the possibility of using carbonate and dolomitic material obtained from the waste of ornamental stone cultivations and more. To this end, tests are underway in the laboratory on materials obtained from 6 different extraction sites subjected to thermal stress and chemical aggression through freeze-thaw cycles and soaking in a sulfuric acid solution with different levels of acidity.

To verify the evolution of the alteration, the samples were subjected to thermal and imbibition cycles of different durations and then subjected to geotechnical and geophysical tests, both destructive and non-destructive. Uniaxial compression tests, indirect tensile tests, Los Angeles tests, Duval tests are carried out on virgin and treated material to carry out comparisons. At the same time, analyses are carried out on thin sections under the microscope to analyse variations in the microstructure of the material.

The experimentation is conducted in agreement and financially supported by the RFI (Italian railway network) and by the 6 supplier quarries and is conducted in the laboratory after a careful verification of the on-site sampling.

Materials and Methods

The tested material is white fine-medium-grained Carrara marble, mainly composed of calcite grains, with minor dolomite and trace amounts of terrigenous minerals. A total of 13 prismatic samples 60x30x30 mm, were prepared from six 60x60x60mm cubic blocks (see Fig. 1 a). These samples were grouped into four groups. The first group was used as untreated bases, while the second, third, and fourth groups were subjected to acid rain chemical weathering simulation for 3, 7, and 28 days, respectively.

This study simulated sulfuric acid rain-induced chemical weathering for 3, 7, and 28 days of exposure. The samples were washed with clean deionized water. Then, they were immersed in a 5×10^{-6} mol/l acid solution of pH 5 inside a rectangular bath (see Fig. 1b). The acid bath was then placed inside a protected environment covered by glasses (see Fig. 1c). After 3 days of acid bath exposure, the samples belonging to the second set were removed from the solution. They were carefully rinsed with clean water and dried in an oven at 105 °C. The third and fourth sets of specimens were kept in the solution for 7 and 28 days, respectively, and were then rinsed and dried in the same manner.

The uniaxial compressive strength (UCS), stress-strain curve, and tangential Young's modulus were determined for untreated and treated samples. These tests were performed using the

Matest compressive servo plus testing machine in the Applied Geology Laboratory of the Department of Earth Sciences at the University of Turin. The machine has a maximum load capacity of 300 kN and the tests were performed under displacement control. Axial displacement was measured throughout the test using an axial LVDT. Axial stress was applied at a constant rate of 0.036- 0.037 mm/min (corresponding to a strain rate of 10⁻⁵/s) with a pre-loading of 2 kN.

DIC analysis (Blaber et al., 2015; Caselle et al., 2019; Ferrero & Migliazza, 2009; Stirling et al., 2013; Zhang et al. 2020), was performed after UCS tests. The lateral surfaces of the samples were cleaned, and a rectangle line was drawn on the sample surface using a permanent black marker to help the software track deformations. For each sample, two videos were recorded on two adjacent lateral faces before and during loading until sample failed, using two optical cameras (see Fig. 1e) with the assistance of Basler video recording open-source software installed on laptops (see Fig. 1d). Each video frame was extracted using the open-source free video-to-JPG converter software. For each video, 9-18 frames were then selected corresponding to specific moments of the stress-strain curve (e.g., elastic phase, strain onset, peak, post-peak) and subsequently analyzed through DIC analysis principles using the Ncorr software (Blaber et al., 2015) coupled with MATLAB R2024b. Strain maps derived from digital image correlation analysis are presented according to Ncorr sign convention.

Fig. 1 a) The 24 samples used in this study before and b) after immersion in the acid solution under the lab glass-covered hood (c), d) Laptop configuration, and e) uniaxial compressive strength apparatus and cameras set up

Result and Discussion

Uniaxial compressive strength and elastic modulus

Fig. 2 reports the number of acid bath days against the mean UCS (see

Fig. 2a) and the mean tangent Young modulus (see

Fig. 2b). The result indicates that UCS decreases as the days of acid bath exposure increase (see

Fig. 2a), identifying a linear relationship. Similarly, tangent Young's modulus also showed a linear decline with acid bath exposure (see

Fig. 2b). The reduction in mechanical strength, and loss of material stiffness after treatment shows the progressive degradation of marble samples. Thus, Carrara marble is vulnerable to degradation under acidic environments, which can aggravate structural vulnerabilities, causing wear, deformation, and failure.

Fig. 2 Relationship between a) mean uniaxial compressive strength and acid bath exposure days and b) mean tangent Young's modulus and acid bath exposure days

Stress-strain curves present how acid exposure affects the behaviour of marble under uniaxial compression (see

Fig. 3). Initially, the stress-strain relationship is non-linear, possibly due to the closure of existing micro-fractures. Untreated samples show relatively higher peak stress, and steepest elastic slope, indicating greater compressive strength. In contrast, for samples exposed to an acid bath, peak stress, and elastic slope relatively decrease with increased acid bath exposure, suggesting the weakening of materials.

The strain behavior of 0, 3, and 7 days of acid-treated samples generally show less strain at peak stress. Samples after 28 days of acid bath display higher strain before failure and lower in peak stress. The strain at peak stress for most samples occurs between 0.0048 and 0.009. The untreated samples reach their peak stress around 0.005-0.008 strain, indicating failure at low deformation. The treated samples particularly after 28 days of acid bath reached their peak around 0.0095 strain, indicating slightly higher strain values than other samples, which failed at high deformation. Although strains show variability across samples, generally it increases as acid bath exposure increases. The post-peak behavior is characterized by numerous resistance drops (see

Fig. 4,

, and **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**), suggesting a stick-slip behavior, consistent with what has been observed at the laboratory scale by several authors in different lithology's (e.g., Caselle et al. 2020).

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curves a) 0 days of acid bath b) 3 days of acid bath c) 7 days of acid bath and d) 28 days of acid bath

Fig. 4 shows strain maps (iii) in the horizontal axis at different stages of loading corresponding to points labeled on stress-strain curves a-n (see Fig. 4i) representing various phases of deformation for an untreated sample. As can be seen from

Fig. 4iii, the results show a relatively uniform distribution of strains (the blue color, corresponds to low strain) with some localizations that become more evident and coherent after reaching the peak. Around point d-e, strains are propagated and relatively well distributed. Strains at points e-f, light blue, green, yellow, and red zones are more localized, indicating the beginning of damage. They (g-n) become increasingly localized into intensive isolated red zones, typically, at point n, strains are fully concentrated with macroscopic crack development and eventual failure. These fracture progression zones reflect the propagation and widening of fractures. The combined result of the stress-strain curve and DIC maps reveal the mechanical behavior of the sample under uniaxial compressive loading. The relatively uniform strain in the early stages indicates a relatively homogenous response. However, the post-peak fracture development phase does not occur homogeneously but is characterized by “jumps”, which are also clearly evident in the stress-strain curve (see

Fig. 4i), suggesting a stick-slip type of behavior.

In general terms, the Digital Image Correlation results highlight brittle fracture mechanisms for the untreated samples, with very clear strain localizations in the maps (see

Fig. 4iii). The sample failure occurs following tensile strain concentrations localized in a few sample areas. The photographic image of the post-failure sample (see

Fig. 4ii) shows the presence of two very well-defined coalescent failure planes consistent with the brittle nature identified by the stress-strain curve and with the location of the high-strain concentration zones identified by the DIC maps (see

Fig. 4iii).

Fig. 4 i) Stress-strain curves ii) sample after the peak , iii) digital image correlation strain maps in horizontal axis (E_{xx}) of untreated samples

This study investigated the effects of sulphuric acid exposure on the mechanical behavior of marble. The changes in uniaxial compressive strength, elastic modulus, and strain evolution during loading were experimentally studied. The uniaxial compressive strength and elastic modulus significantly decrease as the number of days of acid bath exposure increases. Similarly, the failure mechanism is significantly affected by the acid treatment. These results suggested that the mechanical properties of Carrara marble deteriorate due to the acid treatment.

Untreated samples show high peak stress, relatively steep elastic slope, and post-peak sharp stress drop compared to treated samples. In post-peak, both untreated and treated samples show stick-slip behaviour, which could be due to fracture propagation, coalescence, and stress redistribution. The stress-strain curve, in conjunction with DIC strain maps, highlights the stages of deformation, which start with crack initiation, propagation, and coalescence, eventually leading to the failure of the marble samples under uniaxial compression.

The early stages (compaction and elastic) are characterized by uniform strain distribution and minimal damage, while the post-peak stages are predominantly marked by significant strain localization and extensive fracturing. This indicates that DIC is a powerful tool for understanding strain evolution and provides valuable insight into tracking the failure mechanism of rocks under compression. Based on DIC analysis and experiment, fracture evolution increases as the sample approaches failure, with samples experiencing shear, and tensile failures.

The reduction in both UCS and Et after prolonged acid bath exposure underscores the importance of considering and assessing the chemical resistance of rock in engineering design and preservation of historical buildings. This study mainly focused on the effects of acid exposure on the mechanical strength and deformation behaviour of marble rock. In future work, the microscopic changes of marble after the acid exposures and freeze-thaw cycling will be assessed in detail using scanning electron microscopy, digital image correlation, and micro-computed tomography.

Research Team C

The project is aimed at evaluate the feasibility of reuse different types of waste into the traditional ceramic production.

- 1) The first type of investigated waste material is represented by fired ceramic scraps (hereafter FCS). FCS were introduced in the sanitary-ware slip formulation at different levels (6, 12, 15, 18 and 21 wt. %) at the expense of natural raw materials such as feldspar and quartz.

The technological properties of the ceramic body were generally maintained (rheology, WA, shrinkage, mechanical resistance) or improved (deformation) with the exception of the thermal dilation, which was reduced compared to the reference formulation.

XRD Quantitative Phase Analysis and *in-situ* experiments, combined with Scanning Electron Microscopy observations, were able to reveal the reason of this technologically undesired effect. In fact, the increase in the FCS content in the formulation was found to cause (i) a progressive reduction in residual quartz content in the fired body and (ii) a diminution of the alkali content in the glassy matrix that consequently reduces the glass thermal expansion coefficient.

The challenge is now to readjust the formulation to improve the body thermal dilation.

- 2) The second type of investigated waste is represented by bottom ashes (BA) from Municipal

Solid Waste Incinerator plant. Both fine and coarse fractions were considered, due to their different mineralogical composition, and they were introduced at 7 wt.% in the slip formulation in partial replacement of feldspar raw material.

The technological results (rheology, WA, shrinkage and thermal dilation) of the formulation including coarse BA resulted very similar to those of the reference composition. The only exception is represented by mechanical resistance that was reduced by about 10%. In the case of the formulation including fine BA, although the main technological properties (WA and shrinkage) are similar to those of the reference body, some rheological problems due to the presence of not negligible soluble salts were observed. High resolution Synchrotron XRD showed that the mineralogical composition of the fired body is maintained more similar to the reference in the case of coarse BA rather than fine BA. Leaching test according with UNI EN 12457-2 showed that heavy metals concentration in eluates were within the limits for inert waste of Decreto Legislativo 3/9/2020 n.121 all.4.

The challenge is now to confirm these results to other BA batches.

Research Team D

Struvite Production

The project is focused on the recovery of nitrogen (N) and phosphorous (P) from the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW), widely produced during the whole year (58 million tons/year in Europe) and normally disposed of via landfilling. OFMSW can be treated with anaerobic digestion to produce biomethane, a green energy source, and digestate, rich in plant nutrients. Digestate is normally separated into solid and liquid fractions. The solid can be further treated by composting or other methods, while the liquid is often disposed of. A smart strategy to avoid N and P discharge in water bodies is to precipitate ammonium and phosphate from the digestate liquid fraction as struvite, a natural mineral with composition $\text{NH}_4\text{PO}_4\text{Mg}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which can be used as slow-release fertilizer.

When the digestate is separated into solid and liquid fractions, N is typically present in higher amounts in the liquid fraction, while P concentrates in the solid one. However, to be recovered as struvite, P must be solubilized and moved to the liquid part. Various pre-treatments were hence applied on the starting substrate before anaerobic digestion, aiming at solubilizing phosphorus to promote its recovery as struvite and degrading organic matter to boost the energy production of the anaerobic digestion.

After several experimental trials, hydrodynamic cavitation was selected as physical pretreatment. This process can be applied by passing the liquid substrate through a constricted channel at a specific flow velocity or by mechanical rotation, generating bubbles that implode producing regions of high local temperature and pressure, which can break cells and degrade the organic matter. Herein, hydrocavitation was performed on a ROTOCAP hydrodynamic cavitator (E_PIC® Srl, Mongrando, Italy) for 10 minutes at 3000 rpm and 2,5 kW, reaching a temperature of 40°C.

Three enzymatic pretreatments were chosen for the test as well:

- I. USC4, a commercial mixture of cellulase, hemicellulose and protease utilized to simplify the organic matter in the substrate
- II. phosphatase, which catalyzes phosphate hydrolysis
- III. phytase, targeting the hydrolysis of inositol hexaphosphates, organic forms of P produced by plants and microorganisms.

The pretreatments were applied on the substrate, alone or in combination, before performing anaerobic digestion. The effect of the pretreatments was assessed in an experimental trial of anaerobic digestion. The OFMSW was divided into batches of 150 g each, inside 2L glass bottles. Both the untreated substrate and the substrate previously hydrocavitated were tested. The enzymes were dispersed in deionized water and the enzymatic solution was added to the

OFMSW batches. The quantity of USC4 was 2 mL/100 g of substrate dry matter, as recommended by the supplier. The amount of phytase and phosphatase utilized was calculated to achieve total hydrolysis of the organic phosphorous within two hours. The bottles containing substrate and enzymes were incubated for 2 hours at 37°C. After that, the inoculum was added in ratio substrate: inoculum = 1:1 considering the volatile solids. Nitrogen was fluxed inside each bottle for 15 minutes to reach anaerobiosis, then the batches were brought back to the incubator at 37°C and the digestion was conducted for 28 days. Each condition was tested in duplicate, and the biogas production was frequently monitored during the trial.

The digestates were then separated into solid and liquid fraction via centrifugation for 10 minutes at 3500 rpm. The liquid fraction was analyzed and utilized as substrate for the precipitation of struvite. 100 mL of digestate liquid fraction were filtered through a filter paper and transferred into a 250 mL bottle. MgO and KH₂PO₄ were added to reach the N:P:Mg molar ratio 1:1:2 and the pH was adjusted to 9 with NaOH. After 1 hour of stirring, the mixture was centrifuged for 5 minutes at 3000 rpm and then filtered under vacuum to separate the solid struvite and the purified digestate liquid fraction. The struvite was dried at room temperature in a desiccator for a week and then analyzed with X-ray diffraction to determine its crystallinity, scanning electron microscopy to observe its morphology, Kjeldahl analyzer for the total nitrogen content, colorimetric analyses with malachite green to quantify the phosphorous, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry for the magnesium and potassium content and elemental analysis for the carbon content. The content of ammonium, phosphate and magnesium in the digestate liquid fraction was assessed before and after the precipitation of struvite, to determine the nutrient recovery efficiency of the process.

Research Team E

One of the waste disposal challenges within the equine sector is the management of equine bedding wastes. To our best knowledge, no studies have been carried out on horse manure (dung and urine are mixed with the bedding material) to prepare biochar for energy applications. The aim of the study was to apply the pyrolysis/activation thermochemical processes on equine bedding wastes to evaluate their suitability as materials for energy storage (specifically, for solid state hydrogen storage and electrodes for electrochemical devices).

Three different types of bedding wastes (dung and urine mixed with rice husks, straw and sawdust) were collected and analysed for pH, ammonia and nitrates concentration, total carbon and total nitrogen, carbonates and metal contents. Each parameter was tested for normal distribution and the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used, revealing no differences between the three types of horse manure. The same samples were processed at laboratory scale by applying thermochemical processes (i.e. pyrolysis and KOH activation). The raw samples were cut in 0.5 cm in length fragments and further milled in an electric miller. The obtained powders were characterized by infrared spectroscopy to verify the presence of the above quoted polymers and by thermogravimetric analyses, in order to identify the final temperature for the decomposition processes, that was found to be 600 °C for all the samples. This value was chosen for the pyrolysis, performed under nitrogen for 6 h. For the samples prepared with wood shaving, a very small yield in the production of C based biochar was found, confirmed by TGA measurements (average 8 wt% of residue). For the samples obtained from rice waste, yields up to 20 wt% have been recorded. A chemical/thermal activation was performed by mixing the biochar with KOH pellets in a 1:6 weight ratio, heating under Ar up to 250 °C and subsequently to 800 °C with 1 h isotherm for each temperature step. The obtained solid was washed with 0.6 M HCl and distilled water up to neutrality and then dried in a furnace overnight. Activated carbon samples with specific surface area up to 1200 m² /g have been obtained, whose X-Ray powder diffraction patterns were mainly amorphous, with the clear appearance of the graphitic C peak. Hydrogen adsorption tests performed at 77 K by increasing the hydrogen pressure from vacuum to 20 bar showed a reversible hydrogen sorption up to 1.5 wt % with very fast kinetics (0.5 min for adsorption and 1 min for desorption).

Work is in progress to decorate the carbon surface with alkali and transition metal to allow higher working temperatures and gravimetric capacity, to meet the parameters for practical applications. Currently, the research team is working on a laboratory scale, and it is expected to activate a pilot site for testing the materials in a hydrogen storage tank.

Limitations: - the amount of adsorbed hydrogen and the working temperature are still far from practical applications: optimization of the materials by decoration with metals is needed to improve the storage performance; the developed procedure is not completely green (production of CO₂ and CH₄ during the thermal treatments) and it has still a high energy cost (heating steps); - the use of a concentrate basic chemical for activation is to be replaced by green methods (algae treatments are under consideration).

Research Team E

Hazelnut skin

In line with circular economy principles, the re-use of food supply by-products for livestock feed has gained attention. Hazelnut skins (HS), a by-product of hazelnut roasting, are nutritionally valuable, containing fiber, unsaturated fatty acids, phenolic compounds, and tocopherols, which provide antioxidant effects. While HS employment as feed ingredient has been tested with positive outcomes in dairy cows and sheep, no data exist for beef cattle. This project aims to explore HS as a feed option for beef cattle, addressing this gap and advancing sustainable agricultural practices.

The main objective of this project is the evaluation of the inclusion of HS in Piedmontese beef cattle diet, and the analysis of the effects on the whole productive chain.

Four sub-aims can be identified:

- *In vivo* effects on livestock performances, blood parameters and oxidative status, and health status
- *Post mortem* evaluations on the carcass traits and meat quality and safety.
- Feed and meat lipid oxidation and total phenolic content (TPC) evaluations.
- Sensorial evaluation and consumer engagement.

The *in vivo* study approved by the Bioethics Committee of the University of Turin (protocol n.0513042-03/10/2022) began on the 1st of June 2023 and ended on the 7th of October 2024.

A total of 80 Piedmontese beef bullocks aged 7,5±1 month of age was involved and distributed in 8 groups of 10 animals each: 4 control groups (CTR), 4 test groups (HS). All groups were fed iso-energetic and iso-nitrogenous diets divided in two phases: fattening diet until reaching 12±1 months of age, and a finishing diet until slaughter.

The diets administered present the dietary ingredients are reported in Table 1

Table 1. Fattening concentrate composition

Nutrient	CTRL		HS	
	%	kg	%	kg
Coarse corn meal	0,636	4,77	0,562	4,215
Proteic soybean meal	0,045	0,3375	0,045	0,3375
Sunflower meal	0,055	0,4125	0,055	0,4125
Beet pulp	0,049	0,3675	0,049	0,3675
Bran	0,053	0,3975	0,053	0,3975
Whear distiller	0,052	0,39	0,052	0,39
Barley	0,055	0,4125	0,049	0,3675

Extruded flaxseeds	0,003	0,0225	0,003	0,0225
Hydrogenated fat	0,003	0,0225	0,003	0,0225
Coalvitor Proteo	0,025	0,1875	0,025	0,1875
Buffer	0,005	0,0375	0,005	0,0375
Multi acid dry	0,009	0,0675	0,009	0,0675
Urofast	0,01	0,075	0,01	0,075
HS	0	0	0,08	0,6
	1	7,5	1	7,5

The *in vivo* trial ended in October 2024 and in November/December laboratory analyses and consumer test have been conducted.

Preliminary results showed that HS dose not impair the growth performance (Body weight, average daily gain, feed conversion efficiency) and health status (blood analyses and oxidation) of the animals and the HS feed contains higher level of phenolic compounds (measured by Folin-Ciocalteu) compared to control feed. One interesting result to be confirmed by more in-depth analyses is represented by the forage/concentrate ration in the groups. It seems that, thanks to its richness in digestible fiber, the HS groups consumed less straw and hay compared to control. This could extern positive effects on both environmental and economical sustainability of beef diets.

Two main limitations arose during the concluded year:

- One is linked to the absence of the HS quotation in the market. Farmer hosting the trial showed enthusiasms and even if willing to continue the administration of HS to his bullock, this has resulted not possible at the moment
- The other is the seasonality of the product. As many agro-industrial by-products, HS availability is linked to the biological cycle of the hazelnut. This could represent a limit and investigation about HS storage in feed plant or farms should be conducted.

Further data will be available later when statistical methods will be defined and applied.

Research Team G

Rice bran and straw, bean pods, melon and pumpkin peels, typical wastes from our regions, have been obtained by local farmers and submitted to a biological pre-treatment by six strains of wood decay fungi: *Abortiporus biennis*, *Bjerkandera adusta*, *Irpex lacteus*, *Perenniporia fraxinea*, *Schizophyllum commune* and *Trametes versicolor*. All tested strains are conserved in the research fungal culture collection of the Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences – Pavia University. Pre-treatment consists in the colonization of a known amount of the wastes (quantity depending on type of waste, volume occupied and humidity) by the chosen fungal strains by inoculation of a water-mycelium suspension. Inoculated wastes were incubated for two weeks at 25 °C in the dark.

After this step, the materials were subjected to pyrolysis at 450 °C for time ranging from 2 h to 6 h under N₂ flux, obtaining a biochar with specific surface area of few m²/g. For a comparison, thermal treatments at the same temperature and up to 650 °C were performed also on the as received wastes. The pyrolysis yields increased from an average of 15-20% for the not treated wastes at 450 °C (maximum 30% at 650 °C) up to 40% for the biological treated samples. The biochar was then subjected to chemical activation with KOH, in weight ratio 6:1 with respect to the biochar and subsequent thermal treatment at 650 °C for 2 h, obtaining C based-materials with specific surface area up to 2000 m²/g able to adsorb up to 4% of hydrogen at 77 K in a reversible way and with very interesting kinetics (less than 1 minute for hydrogenation and maximum 1.5 minute for dehydrogenation). The decoration of these activated carbons with Ni

by chemical impregnation starting from Ni salts led to the obtainment of Ni nanoparticles on the C surface with ability to chemisorb small amount of hydrogen at 200 °C. Work is in progress on the optimization of the decoration process.

The limits of the developed procedure are that it is not completely green (production of CO₂ and CH₄ during the thermal treatments) and it has still a high energy cost. Moreover, the use of a concentrate basic chemical for activation is to be replaced by green methods (algae treatments are under consideration).

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